

Effective Methods of using Digital Technologies in the Field of Tourism

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the effective methods of using digital technologies in the field of tourism. Also, the author's approaches and proposals for the use of digital technologies in the field of tourism are presented.*

Key words: *artificial intelligence, diversification, virtual tourism, geolocation clocks, transport-logistics, gastronomic tourism, ethnographic tourism.*

Introduction. Nowadays, the use of digital technologies based on best practices in the field of tourism remains important. In particular, the use of digital technologies in the subjects of the world's tourism market is growing year by year. The use of digital technologies is a new form of communication between producers and consumers of tourist services and is becoming a source of competitive advantages of tourist organizations. The global tourism industry is experiencing radical changes related to technology. The analysis shows that between the 2000s and today, technological advances have significantly changed the process of researching and booking travel services. Digital technologies are becoming the main direction of strategy development for the development of culture and tourism in cities, as well as urbanization processes.

Digital technologies contribute to the rapid integration of urban tourists into the urban environment and allow them to independently plan their trips, communicate with local residents through headsets with simultaneous translation, visit museums and places of recreation and entertainment. will greatly help them to receive personal recommendations.

The potential of digitalization of business in the field of tourism depends on the financial and technological capabilities of each subject and the industry as a whole. In recent years, the tourism market of Uzbekistan has significantly increased its size. In our country, online booking services have serious growth prospects, while classic travel agencies will remain available. Tourism is currently one of the largest and most promising sectors of the world economy. It plays an important role in the creation of jobs, in the export earnings of many countries, and in the overall contribution to the gross domestic product. Existing political differences, sanctions, regional conflicts, and the number of international tourist destinations are steadily growing year by year.

Review of literature on the subject.

Foreign scientists such as L. Cantoni, J. Pesonen, M. Sigala, H. Werthner, have developed and consistently implemented a holistic concept of tourism development, given tourism the status of a strategic sector of the economy, and accelerated the development of this field in a comprehensive manner, involving all regions and related industries. Diversification of the economy, which should become the leading force of development, implementation of measures to stimulate entrepreneurial activity in the tourism sector and development of competition in the market of tourism services, improvement of the statistical accounting system in the tourism sector, rapid development of tourism

in the country, from the existing huge tourism potential more complete and effective use, together with traditional cultural-historical tourism, other potential types of tourism - pilgrimage, ecological, educational, ethnographic, gastronomic, sports, treatment-health, rural, industrial, business tourism and issues such as the rapid development of other types, the strengthening of the social importance of tourism due to the development of children, teenagers and youth tourism, family tourism, social tourism for the elderly have been studied.

Popkova Ye.G., Shichkina A.A., Kuznesova O.V. from CIS scientists. in a number of scientific works, he introduced scientific innovations on the trends and future prospects of the use of digital technologies in tourism, and today, in his research, he is conducting effective research on creating a tourism brand through social networks. Also, Morze, N., Ivanov, S., Pizlo.O, in their scientific works mainly econometric analysis of the tourism industry by indicators and factors, and a number of practical works on providing cheap and high-quality services based on programming implemented.

Local scientists Khamidov O.Kh., Jurayev A.T., Yavmutov D.Sh., Rakhimov O.Kh., Nurov Z.S., O. Radjabov are interested in the tourism attractiveness of our country, especially the tourism opportunities of the Bukhara region, pilgrimage, ecological, educational, ethnographic, gastronomic, sports, health care. They carried out scientific research on the rapid development of urbanization, rural, industrial, business tourism and other types, promotion of children, teenagers and youth tourism, family tourism, social tourism for the elderly. In addition, the trends in the use of digital technologies in the field of tourism, the main principles of the travel planning system using digital platforms, the establishment of the foundations of sustainable tourism, world experience in the use of digital technologies in reducing the negative impact on the environment and public health, The methodological importance of the digital marketing network in increasing the tourism attractiveness of the Bukhara region, promoting the tourist centers of the Bukhara region as a brand in social networks, the importance of creating virtual tourism content for the tourist objects of the Bukhara region, economic efficiency based on the use of digital technologies and artificial intelligence in tourism. It should be noted separately that studies on the analysis of risks arising in the development of the tourism industry on the basis of digital technologies have not been carried out. From this point of view, the above issues are considered important in the development of tourism industry of Bukhara region.

The main part.

The global tourism industry is undergoing fundamental changes related to technology. In recent decades, technologies development has fundamentally changed the quality of tourist services. Consequently, information plays an important role in attracting tourists. In this regard Application of digital technologies in the development of tourism in Uzbekistan it is considered one of the main factors for a positive solution to this important task. The introduction of digital technologies plays an important role in increasing the competitiveness of the industry and introducing potential tourists to the tourism potential of Uzbekistan.

The new opportunities that are opening up for people thanks to the development of the digital economy are undoubtedly positive changes that open up new opportunities in almost all spheres of activity. With the development of digital technologies, the consumer can receive the ordered services faster and also save money, because the prices on the Internet are often lower than those offered by offline businesses. Another vivid example is buying an electronic version of a book, which is much cheaper than a printed analogue. In addition, everyone has the opportunity to agree with other buyers and buy the desired product at a wholesale price. Thus, a huge amount can be saved in a year. Another important advantage is the opportunity to start your own business from the comfort of your home.

Currently, it is known that the tourism sector, which is the most active in the introduction of digital technologies, is becoming more advanced in the process of involving information technologies in the sector. Because the use of new modern technologies in the field of tourism serves as an important basis for creating a comfortable and efficient environment in the future.

Compared to more familiar forms of management, this method can influence the efficiency of certain types of production, technologies and equipment. Based on research by Booking.ru, the world's

population is interested in artificial intelligence and smart technologies. Today, chatbots can replace live communication with a consultant, as they are able to answer various questions of users, for example, Kayak - the chatbot provides recommendations and travel advice, taking into account the user's available budget, from purchasing airline tickets. However, the use of mobile devices and mobile applications significantly simplifies the work of tourism enterprises, because personalization in the field of customer service allows organizations to collect the necessary information about the structure of customer spending, their preferences, and interests, as well as other information that allows us to conduct various marketing studies, resulting in the improvement of the quality of the services provided. Digitization of tourism is taking many forms, including the online purchase of ready-made tours designed by tour operators and individual tours designed for tour operators and tourists through mobile applications or computer software systems.

Modern digital technologies are bringing fundamental changes to the travel industry, breaking new ground for travelers and making the travel experience more convenient and flexible.

Mobile apps have become an integral part of travel, offering a wide range of features from finding and booking accommodation to planning itineraries and searching for local restaurants and attractions. Voice recognition and artificial intelligence technologies make it possible to create unique personalized recommendations that match the individual preferences of travelers.

Online platforms for sharing housing and services such as Airbnb, Booking.com and other similar platforms are modernizing the traditional hotel industry, offering unique accommodation options and the possibility of autonomous travel.

Virtual reality and augmented reality are changing the way travelers plan and perceive the places they want to visit. Virtual tours and interactive maps allow travelers to explore places in advance and make informed travel decisions.

Thus, digital technologies have a great impact on the tourism industry, creating new opportunities for travelers and ways to improve the supply of the industry as a whole. This forces the tourism industry to constantly adapt to the changing needs of consumers and create innovative solutions to improve the tourist experience.

Currently, the wide distribution and development of global sources of information exchange allows to accurately analyze the wishes of tourists, taking into account the places they visit. This shows that tourism business development is achieving significant positive indicators. As an example of this, we can cite the fact that attributes in the field of tourism, combined with modern technologies, are entering our lives, such as geolocation watches, mobile guides, ticket payment programs, and virtual reality technologies.

Most importantly, the function of modern software can quickly respond to the requirements of the tourist, help him to search for the destination and evaluate the tourist attractions of the country, and based on this information, he can create the profile of the tourist, the objects to be visited, the time of visiting the tourist places and consists of analyzing other data. Now, since there is almost no special time and material costs for conducting surveys among tourists and their statistical processing, we mainly analyze the tourist attraction from the Internet, anticipate changes in trends and make sure that the existing tourist offers meet the needs of the client. we can use to do.

Research methodology.

Methods such as induction and deduction, comparison and SWOT analysis were used in the process of writing the article.

Analysis and results.

Digital marketing has become an important part of today's economy as a means of promoting a product or service. Each major segment of the market is developing with the help of digital technologies, using them we have the opportunity to increase the volume of sales, increase the reputation of the brand and create certain trends related to the activity of the company or organization.

By applying digital technologies in the tourism sector, digital advertising is serving as an effective tool in the tourism sector.

Digital Marketing: Digital marketing involves using digital channels such as social media, search engines, email marketing and mobile apps to promote tourism services. Effective digital marketing strategies can help tourism businesses reach a wider audience, improve their online presence and increase market share.

Digital Customer Relationship Management (CRM): Digital CRM tools help tourism businesses manage their customer relationships by collecting and analyzing customer data. This helps businesses gain insights into customer behavior that they can use to tailor services and improve customer satisfaction.

Globally, there has been an increase in tourist flows in the last six years, and by 2030 it is expected that there will be about 350 million international tourist exchanges, according to UNWTO, the number of domestic and foreign tourists (arrivals - departures) is about 1.8 reaches a billion.

As a result of the pandemic, tourism activity has decreased by 50%, the forecast of total export revenue from international tourism has significantly decreased, but by 2024, the situation is close to the situation before the COVID-19 pandemic, according to the analysis.

According to the Master card Global Destination Index, the total volume of tourists to the visited country from around the world reached 140.3% in 2009-2018, and the total volume of income from tourists was 176%. It is known from the analysis that tourism expenses have increased by 197%. In 2019, the share of tourism activity in the source of income of the world economy increased from 3% to 4%, and in Europe, an increase of 6% was achieved. The figures published by the World Tourism Organization show that the total export income from international tourism per year is growing at an average of 4 percent. It can be seen that tourism has become one of the most important economic sectors today. Therefore, many countries of the world are taking all measures to further develop this industry, create relevant infrastructure at the level of world standards and increase the flow of tourists.

Today, France (80 million on average per year), USA (75 million), Spain (65 million), China (55 million) and Italy (45 million) are in the top five. Germany, Great Britain, Turkey and Mexico are among the top ten. Also, several European and Asian cities are leading according to this indicator. Examples of this are cities such as Hong Kong (30 million on average per year), London (18 million), Singapore (17 million), Bangkok (16 million) and Paris (15 million).

Unfortunately, it can be seen that Uzbekistan is still far behind in this field. In particular, according to the assessment given by the World Tourism and Travel Council (WTC), Uzbekistan ranks 150th among the countries in terms of tourist visits.

Despite the fact that our country has a place in the world tourist market, the level of creating comfortable conditions for tourists, improving service, increasing the attractiveness of tourist attractions, and strengthening advertising is very low. Therefore, thinking about a significant increase in this regard depends on these factors.

On December 22, 2017, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his Address to the Parliament, made the following comments about the tourism industry among all other sectors:

"Today, tourism is one of the promising industries that bring high income to the national economy. Uzbekistan is a country with great potential in the field of tourism. There are more than 7,300 objects of cultural heritage in our country, and nearly 200 of them are included in the UNESCO list.

At the same time, it is possible to open new tourist destinations using the opportunities of our country's unique nature and beautiful resorts. Actively involving world brands in this field, we need to pay special attention to the development of pilgrimage tourism, ecological, educational, ethnographic, gastronomic tourism and other branches of this field. In this regard, we should take into account that the use of public-private partnership relations opens wide opportunities for the development of the industry.

It is necessary to develop and accelerate the program of visiting holy places and monuments in Samarkand, Bukhara, Khorezm regions and Tashkent cities. It is necessary to fully utilize the great opportunities in the field of domestic tourism."

Conclusions and suggestions.

The development of the digital economy will significantly change many types of economic activity, including the provision of infrastructure for tourism. Considering that the basis of the digital economy is large-scale information processing, a high-tech system of information storage, processing and transmission is of particular importance. In order to provide convenience to potential tourists, we should expect the active development of mobile technologies that provide a wide range of functions, such as purchasing airline tickets, booking hotels, traveling around the area, providing information about attractions, cultural and historical heritage, and providing ratings. The digital economy creates an opportunity to potentially create new forms of tourism businesses. There will also be serious changes in the field of personnel infrastructure. Our social life and tourist activities are becoming increasingly technological, forming a new unified information space in the field of world tourism, and developing a system of information provision and tourism management.

Also, the Decree of the head of our state dated December 2, 2016 "On measures to ensure the rapid development of the tourism sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan" is significant because it aims to eliminate the errors and shortcomings encountered in the sector and to develop it consistently.

When the President spoke about tourism in the Address dedicated to the main results of the socio-economic development of our country in 2019 and the most important priority directions of the economic program for 2020, the development of such a lucrative sector is being neglected, its O' He emphasized the need to take concrete measures to increase the contribution to the development of Uzbekistan's economy, promote our historical and cultural values, and replenish foreign exchange reserves.

The trends and problems of using digital technologies in the field of tourism are constantly in need of scientifically based research and proposals - recommendations. A number of literature and scientific works have been created on digitalization of tourism services. In particular, Bournemouth University professor Dimitras Buchalis focused his research on the creation of value added chains and their digitization in all processes in tourism, travel, hospitality and catering. University of Southern California professor Ulrike Gresel has created scientific works on the introduction of information technologies into the traditional tourism network and the creation of safe tourism routes based on digital tourism.

In conclusion, in all regions of the Republic, especially in the Bukhara region, tourism industry facilities that meet modern world standards, the needs and requirements of tourists - hotels and similar means of accommodation, public catering facilities, transport and logistics structures, information centers, culture and rapid development of sports institutions, rapid construction and reconstruction of road transport and engineering-communication infrastructure, road infrastructure in the main tourism directions, attracting foreign investors for these purposes is still an issue today. is lib. Taking into account the trends of international tourism development and the use of modern marketing tools, developing competitive tourism products and services, developing a strategy for promoting them in the domestic and international tourism markets, organizing and developing a favorable tourism information environment, wide a number of practical works on creating a positive image of our country in the field of tourism by conducting advertising and information activities, opening tourism information centers in the regions of the country and tourism representative offices abroad, actively using the Internet, holding an international tourism fair every year is being implemented. Fundamental improvement of the system of quality training of qualified personnel, especially in the field of management and marketing, training of guides (excursion leaders), regular retraining and upgrading of the employees of tourism activities are on the constant agenda for the tourism industry. The above-mentioned issues are relevant today among the modern trends in the use of digital technologies in the field of tourism.

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